

INVESTIGATING COATING TRANSFER IN DRUG-COATED BALLOON ANGIOPLASTY THROUGH A COUPLED IN VITRO AND IN SILICO ANALYSIS

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1. Introduction

Drug-coated balloons (DCBs) have emerged as a potential treatment option for arterial lesions due to their ability to deliver uniform drug-coating to the arterial wall. However, some clinical studies have demonstrated inferior efficacy compared to drug-eluting stents, possibly due to restrained coating delivery (1), as confirmed by recent animal studies which revealed sparse and irregular spatial coating distribution (2). To date, no comprehensive method has been developed to assess the influence of arterial features and angioplasty parameters on coating transfer for DCBs. Therefore, this study aimed to develop a strategy that combines numerical and experimental data to investigate the efficacy of coating transfer to the arterial wall during DCB angioplasty.

2. Methods

Figure 1 (top) shows the proposed methodology which includes two approaches at two different scales: i) *in silico* simulations, at the device-artery scale, ii) *in vitro* stamping tests, at the coating-diseased intima scale. The *in silico* approach is based on accurate finite element models of balloons and arteries to investigate their mechanical interaction during the clinical treatment, under various conditions of balloon folding, oversizing, arterial stiffness, and plaque distribution. These models enable the prediction of various factors that influence the performance of DCB treatment, namely: i) contact pressure, associated with coating adhesion to the artery, ii) balloon stretch, associated with coating detachment from the balloon, iii) media/adventitia overstretch, associated to arterial damage. In parallel, innovative *in vitro* setups facilitate the investigation of the coating and arterial intima interaction, by stamping (3) either flat coated patches or DCB rings onto porcine arterial segments with varying properties (Figure 1, top). Several variables can be investigated: contact pressure and time, environmental conditions, balloon stretch, and plaque stiffness. The optical analysis of the post-stamped specimens can be used to determine the transfer rates of the coatings, providing insight into the behavior of different coating types.

3. Results

Figure 1 (bottom) illustrates examples of the results that can be obtained by exploiting the developed methodology. On the left, the two computational color maps indicate the spatial heterogeneous contact pressure for two interventional conditions, while on the right, the two experimental images show the effect of two contact pressures on the coating transfer from patches onto healthy pig arterial walls. The combination of these two outputs enables the prediction of the local transfer of the coating to the arterial wall.

4. Conclusion

This study used a combination of numerical simulations and experimental techniques to explore the relationship between procedural parameters and the transfer efficiency of the coating during DCB angioplasty. The DCB performance depends on a complex interplay of balloon and drug coating properties and the arterial and intervention features. A coupled, hybrid approach (*in silico/in vitro*) offers a straightforward method to include all the relevant parameters in the analysis, which may not be feasible with a single strategy. The ultimate goal is to develop a suitable approach for optimizing the planning of the DCB procedure using patient-specific computational simulations and experimental characterization of commercial DCBs.

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5. References

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